

2. Phenograms showing the relationships among the different haplotypes for strains of *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzicola* obtained using a) data and b) *PstI* restriction enzyme analysis.^a

^aStrain designations for representative isolates are shown in parentheses. Strains were grouped using the unweighted pair group method with arithmetic means (UPGMA). The percentage of times that a particular group was formed by bootstrap analysis is shown on each fork of the phenogram.

restriction endonuclease analyses (Fig. 1b). For restriction endonuclease analysis, chromosomal DNA isolated from each strain was digested to completion with *PstI*. High molecular weight (HMW) bands between 23.1 and 7.1 kb were polymorphic between genomes of the strains (Fig. 1b). The number of HMW bands ranged from 5 (in BLS280) to 13 (in BLS30). Thirty-six different banding patterns (*PstI* haplotypes) were resolved by *PstI* digestion.

For RFLP analysis, the probe used was a repetitive DNA sequence contained in plasmid pBluescript that had been isolated from a partial genomic library of *X. oryzae* pv. *oryzicola* strain, BLS335. Clone pR41 was suspected to contain a repetitive DNA element based on the intensity of hybridization in colony blots when probed with labeled genomic DNA from *X. oryzae* pv. *oryzicola*. The repetitive nature of the pR41 insert was confirmed when the clone hybridized to multiple fragments of *PstI*-digested genomic DNA of *X. oryzae* pv. *oryzicola* in Southern blots. The DNA sequence of the pR41 insert (459 nucleotides in length) is 44.8% identical to part of the sequence of a *IS1112*, a mobile, repetitive DNA insertion element cloned from *X. oryzae* pv. *oryzicola*. When Southern blots of *PstI*-digested DNA from the 124 strains of *X. oryzae* pv. *oryzicola* were hybridized with the pR41, 26 different banding patterns (R41 haplotypes) were observed based on 71 total band positions. The genetic diversity of the population of *X. oryzae* pv. *oryzicola*

assessed by RFLP was estimated to be 0.92 by Nei and Tajima's equation. This value is similar to the genetic diversity of a comparable collection of *X. oryzae* pv. *oryzae* strains.

The DNA fingerprints of the 26 different R41 and 36 *PstI* haplotypes were used to estimate the relatedness among the different haplotypes by cluster analyses (unweighted pair group arithmetic average clustering methods, or UPGMA). The robustness of the phenograms was evaluated using the bootstrap procedure (Fig. 2). The haplotypes that defined both R41 and *PstI* did not cluster tightly. Several small clusters of two to three similar haplotypes were seen, but most haplotypes did not belong to clearly defined groups.

Strains representing the haplotypes of *X. oryzae* pv. *oryzicola* were inoculated to rice cultivar IR50 and lesion lengths were measured to determine if groups of the pathogen could be discerned based on aggressiveness (as measured by lesion length). A continuous range of lesion lengths was observed. That is, although infection with strains from different haplotypes resulted in lesions of different lengths, there was overlap in lengths of lesions caused by the various haplotypes and no discrete groupings were formed. To determine if haplotypes are differentially aggressive to other rice varieties and to identify representative isolates for evaluation of germplasm, we are now inoculating strains representing each of the R41 and *PstI* haplotypes to a diverse group of rice varieties. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

ASD19: a medium-duration, short- and slender-grained variety for Tamil Nadu, India

W. Wilfred Manuel, T. Sundaram, K. Ganesan, S. Valravan, P. Shanmugasundaram, K. Mohanasundaram, S. Palanisamy, M. Subramanlan, and M. Rangaswamy, Rice Research Station, (RRS), Ambasamudram 627401, Tamil Nadu, India

ASD19 is a derivative of the cross between Lalnakanda and IR30. It is semidwarf (108 cm) and matures in

120-132 d. It is highly suitable for sowing in Pishanam season (Oct-Feb) in southern districts of Tamil Nadu where IR20 and ADT39 are currently being grown.

In 240 trials conducted at research stations and in farmers' fields in Tamil Nadu and around the nation, ASD19 yielded an average 5.8 t/ha, outperforming all of the checks, including IR20 by 14.2% (Table 1).

In fertilizer trials, 100 kg N/ha was found to be the optimum fertilizer dose for ASD19 (Table 2).

ASD19 possesses moderate resistance to blast and is tolerant of early drought.

It has well-exserted panicles with short, slender grains that have a protein content of 9.6% and good cooking quality. Its milling recovery to total rough rice is 65.5%, 3.8% higher than that of IR20. Its 1,000-grain weight is 18.3 g.

ASD19 was released in January 1995 for general cultivation in Pishanam season in southern districts of Tamil Nadu. (See next page for tables.) ■

Table 1. Grain yield of ASD19. Tamil Nadu, India. 1979-93.

Trial ^a and year	Mean grain yield (t/ha)				
	ASD19	IR20	ADT39	CO 43	Ponni/White Ponni
RRS, Ambasamudram, 1979-93	5.2 (18)	3.8 (18)	3.8 (5)	4.3 (13)	4.4 (14)
Multilocation trials at research stations, 1981-92	4.9 (25)	4.3 (18)	4.0 (1)	5.3 (15)	—
Adaptive research trials in farmers' fields					
Nellai Kattabomman District, 1987-90	5.6 (49)	5.1 (48)	6.8 (10)	5.0 (49)	—
Chidambaranar District, 1987-90	6.9 (28)	6.0 (28)	5.7 (10)	6.3 (28)	—
Kanyakumari District, 1983	4.1 (14)	—	—	3.6 (14)	—
Minikit - Chidambaranar District, 1988, 1992	6.3 (100)	—	—	—	—
National trials - Directorate of Rice Research, 1987, 1990	4.3 (6)	—	—	—	—
Overall mean	5.8	5.0	5.7	5.1	4.4
Trials (no.)	240	112	26	119	14
Corresponding mean yield of ASD19	—	5.7	6.1	5.7	5.0
Increase over checks (%)	—	14.2	8.4	11.9	13.2

^aFigures in parentheses indicate number of trials.

Table 2. Fertilizer trial on ASD19. Tamil Nadu, India. 1991-93.

N level (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)			
	1991	1992	1993	Mean
0	3.4	2.3	4.3	3.3
50	4.6	3.0	4.6	4.1
100	5.4	3.3	4.9	4.5
150	5.0	3.4	5.0	4.5
200	5.9	3.6	5.0	4.8
CD (P= 0.05)	1.5	0.2	0.2	—

IRRN REMINDER

Multiple submissions. Normally, only one report for a single experiment will be accepted. Two or more items about the same work submitted at the same time will be returned for merging. Submitting at different times multiple notes from the same experiment is highly inappropriate. Detection will result in the rejection of all submissions on that research.

Seed technology

Mutagenic effectiveness, efficiency of gamma rays, and genetic parameters of variation in gamma-irradiated upland rice

S. S. Mehetre, P. A. Patil, S. K. Lad, C. R. Mahajan, and P. M. Dhumal, Botany Section, College of Agriculture, Kolhapur 416004, Maharashtra, India

We studied mutagenic effectiveness, efficiency of gamma rays, and genetic parameters in the M₁ and M₂ generations of eight upland rice varieties (HS17, Basmati 371, Jaya, Kundalika, R24, Ghansal, JS180, and ACK5) that were irradiated with gamma rays.

M₀ generation. The experiment was laid out in a factorial randomized block. Dry seeds of the varieties were irradiated at 10, 20, 30, 40, and 50 kR.

M₁ generation. Irradiated seeds were sown along with unirradiated control seeds during 1992 dry season (kharif). Germination and survival percentages (Table 1) were recorded at 10 and 30 d after sowing. Obser-

vations were recorded for different characters (Tables 1 and 2).

Analysis of variance showed significant varietal differences and variety × dose interactions, indicating that the gamma rays induced variation for days to flowering, days to maturity, and grain yield/plant. Seeds were collected from the primary panicles of all surviving M₁ plants. Seed fertility was recorded. As the radiation dose increased from 10 to 50 kR, both germination and survival percentage (except at 30 kR) and plant height (except at 30 kR) decreased compared with the control (Table 1). Grain fertility decreased in all the doses compared with the control.

Genetic components were computed, except for the control, and irradiated varieties and doses were pooled for different characters. Variation ranged from 1.0% (days to maturity) to 20.2% (grains/plants). The greatest range of variation was for grains/plant (20.2%), grain yield/plant (18.0%), and tillers/plant (16.6%), indicating greater scope for genetic improvement in these characters. The

extent of genotypic coefficients of variation (GCV) showed that grain yield/plant (48.3) had the highest GCV followed by 1,000-grain weight (28.2), plant height (24.6), and grains/plant (21.6). High GCV values in these characters proved the existence of high genetic variability in gamma ray-induced varieties.

High broad sense heritability estimates were recorded by all the characters except tillers/plant. High genetic advance was observed for grain yield plant (93.3%), 1,000-grain weight (58.6%), and plant height (48.9%). High heritability along with high genetic advance were most useful in predicting the resultant effect for selecting the best individuals.

Grain yield/plant, 1,000-grain weight, and plant height indicated the presence of additive gene action, which is desirable for the selection process in subsequent generations.

M₂ generation. Seeds were collected from the primary panicles